

GENDER AND ITS PECULIARITIES IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6496781>

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Annotation: *The English language is a member of the Indo-European family of languages which had also influenced its grammar. The language is a complex system that was developing for long centuries and this development is still in progress. The development of English was influenced by some other languages, their grammar and vocabulary. Not only other languages and their impact on English had caused the development of gender marked nominations of person but also the changing society.*

Keywords: *gender, gender marked nominations of person, gender component, category of gender, semantics.*

INTRODUCTION

The status of gender category had been influenced by some other languages and their grammar. If we trace in the history of the English language we will find different categories of gender in different periods of the development of this language. While many Indo-European languages have grammatical gender, English is normally described as lacking of this type of gender, although in the Old English period it was a very productive inflectional category. Gender was no more inflectional category in Modern English¹.

The development of gender marked nominations of person was also influenced by the development of society and by changing roles of males and females in society. Also the rise of feminism had impact on the development of new nominations marked by gender, especially in the employment sphere. In the process of the language development gender had changed its status in grammar and semantics. Tracing in different periods of language development we come to know about the changes and uses of gender category from grammatical in Old English period to natural in Modern English to nowadays.

“The English gender system is unusual in the family of Indo- Germanic languages, as well as among Indo-European languages more generally.”

MATERIALS AND METHODS

¹ Corbett, G. G. *Gender*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011. 384 p., ISBN: 0 52133845 X

According to A. Curzan, Old English had three grammatical genders: masculine, feminine and neuter, and all inanimate nouns belonged to one of the three classes, sometimes for morphological reason, but more often for no obvious reason.

T. Rastorgeyva says the later simplification of noun morphology affected the grammatical categories in different ways and to a varying degree. Gender in Old English as a classifying feature (not being a grammatical category proper) disappeared together with other distinctive features of the noun declensions. While the declension system played a certain role in the decay of the Old English declension system, in Late Old English and Early Middle English nouns were grouped into classes or types of declension according to gender instead of stems. Later development of 11th and 12th centuries brought that gender of nouns was deprived of its main formal support - the weakened and levelled endings of adjectives and adjective pronouns ceased to indicate gender. Semantically, gender was associated with the differentiation of sex and therefore the formal grouping into genders was smoothly and naturally superseded by a semantic division into inanimate and animate nouns with a further subdivision of the letter into males and females².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To prove this here is the example from Chaucer's time when gender was already a lexical category, like in Modern English, nouns are referred to as "he" and "she" if they denote human beings and as "it" when they denote animals or inanimate thing:

She wolde wepe, if that she saw a mous, Cought in a teppe, if it were deed or bledde.

*She points here to a woman while it replaces the noun *mous*, which in Old English was Feminine. ('She would weep, if she saw a mouse caught in a trap, if it was dead or it bled.')*

A. Curzan states that the natural gender system in Modern English, where only nouns referring to males and females generally take gendered pronouns and inanimate objects are neuter, stands as the exception, not the rule among the world's languages.

In other periods of the English language development gender remained the lexical (semantic) category.

"Gender in language, which can be referred to by general term linguistic gender, can be defined at the most basic level as a system of noun classification reflected in behaviour of associated words."

² Curzan, A. Gender shifts in history of English. Cambridge University Press, 2003. 218 p., ISBN: 0 521 82007 3.

Therefore the essential criterion of the linguistic gender is taken to be agreement (or concord), or systematic and predictable covariance between a semantic or formal property of one grammatical form and a formal property of another. This is the example from Old English³:

Seo brade lind wæs tilu and ic hire lufode.

That broad shield was good and I loved her. (literally 'herloved')

The demonstrative pronoun *seo* 'the, that' and the adjectives *brade* 'broad' and *tilu* 'good' appear in their feminine form to agree with the feminine noun *lind* 'shield'; in the second clause, the shield is then referred back to with the feminine pronoun *hire* 'her' in accordance with the noun's grammatical gender. As the Modern English translation demonstrates, this kind of grammatical agreement of gender has been lost, only the personal pronouns still mark gender and it is semantically, not grammatically based.

CONCLUSION

"Gender describes the characteristics that a society or culture delineates as masculine or feminine. In sociological terms 'gender role' refers to the characteristics and behaviours that different cultures attribute to the sexes."

According to P. Kvetko_ there are two types of word meaning: grammatical and lexical one. In grammatical meaning, the component of meaning is expressed by inflectional endings, individual forms or some other grammatical devices, e.g. word order. For example the words "boys, houses, pens", etc., though denoting different objects, have something in common. This common element of the words (expressed by the ending -s) is the grammatical meaning of plurality. As to the lexical meaning, comparing word-forms of one and the same word, we find out that there is another component of meaning - identical in all forms of word, i.e. the meaning of the base (or root) in a set of inflectional forms, e.g.: *go, goes, went, going, gone* (in this case: the component denoting the process of movement). This is the lexical meaning - the component of meaning proper to the word as a linguistic unit, i.e. recurrent in all the forms of this word. The lexical meaning may be understood as a set of basic semantic components (semantic features - semes).

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